

Luminous Flux and solid angle through the vertical circular disk

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Now we view a point light source Q and a circular disk with radius R and distance r to the light source as in the figure. We assume that the whole room is

a vacuum. Then we must look at the belonging sphere with the radius R_k . The

problem is to ascertain the circular disk's solid angle Ω to the light source Q . We introduce one h that is the height of the hatched spherical segment. With the figure we recognize:

$$R_k = r + h \quad r^2 + R^2 = R_k^2 \quad (1)$$

The lateral area of the hatched spherical segment is: $M = 2\pi R_k \cdot h$ We follow:

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = \frac{M}{R_k^2} = 2\pi \frac{h}{R_k} \quad (2)$$

Or if we bear in mind that the solid angle of the whole sphere is 4π sr and the surface of the sphere is $O = 4\pi R_k^2$:

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = \frac{M}{O} \cdot 4\pi = \frac{2\pi R_k \cdot h}{4\pi R_k^2} \cdot 4\pi = 2\pi \frac{h}{R_k}$$

because of (1):

$$R_k - r = h \quad R_k^2 = r^2 + R^2$$

It follows:

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = 2\pi \frac{R_k - r}{R_k} = 2\pi \left(1 - \frac{r}{R_k}\right)$$

R_k inserted:

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = 2\pi \left(1 - \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}}\right) \quad r > 0 \quad (3)$$

With constant luminous intensity I we obtain for the luminous flux Φ through the circle:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi[\text{lm}] &= I[\text{cd}] \cdot \Omega[\text{sr}] \\ \Phi[\text{lm}] &= 2\pi I \left(1 - \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}}\right) \quad r > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Now we derive an approximation for the case $R \ll r$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} &= \sqrt{\frac{r^2}{r^2 + R^2}} = \left(\frac{r^2 + R^2}{r^2}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{R^2}{r^2}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \approx 1 - \frac{R^2}{2r^2} \quad \text{bei } R \ll r \end{aligned}$$

$\approx$ because of $(1+x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \approx 1 - \frac{1}{2}x$ for $|x| \ll 1$ see * at the end of the text. For $R \ll r$ we follow further with (3):

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] \approx 2\pi \left(1 - 1 + \frac{R^2}{2r^2}\right) = \pi \frac{R^2}{r^2}$$

This is the known quadratic approximation for the solid angle Ω .

To the luminous flux:

$$\Phi[\text{lm}] \approx \pi I \frac{R^2}{r^2} \quad R \ll r \quad (5)$$

One approximation of equation (3) for $R \gg r$:

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] \approx 2\pi \left(1 - \frac{r}{R}\right) \quad \text{for } R \gg r$$

This is no quadratic approximation. Now we search a relation between the solid angle and the angle α . (see figure)

after viewing the figure:

$$R_k = r + h = R_k \cdot \cos \alpha + h$$

thus: $h = R_k(1 - \cos \alpha)$

with (2):

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = 2\pi \frac{h}{R_k} = 2\pi(1 - \cos \alpha) \quad (6)$$

or

$$\frac{\Omega[\text{sr}]}{2\pi} = 1 - \cos \alpha$$

$$\cos \alpha = 1 - \frac{\Omega[\text{sr}]}{2\pi}$$

Another unit for the solid angle is the square degree $\square^\circ$. We find a relation between steradian and square degree. Surface of the whole sphere is $O = 4\pi R_k^2$ and the perimeter is $U = 2\pi R_k = 360^\circ$
 $\hat{=}$ mean "according to". $R_k \hat{=} \frac{360^\circ}{2\pi}$ it follows:

$$O \hat{=} 4\pi \left(\frac{360^\circ}{2\pi} \right)^2 \quad O \hat{=} \frac{360^2 \square^\circ}{\pi} \approx 41252.96 \square^\circ$$

The sphere's surface has got a solid angle of 4π steradian. So we have:

$$1\text{sr} = \frac{360^2 \square^\circ}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi} = \frac{360^2}{4\pi^2} \square^\circ = \left(\frac{180}{\pi} \right)^2 \square^\circ$$

$$1\text{sr} \approx 3282.8 \square^\circ$$

One biological remark:

The eye-lens of human beings and of some animals are circular. A part of the lens is covered by the iris (see the following figure).

The non-covered part of the eye-lens is circular. At near point light sources we

can recognize the following because of formula (4): see fig.

The lightness is stronger dependent on the distance, if the eye-lens is smaller.

If the eye lens is bigger, then the dependence on the distance is not so strong. We presuppose here the same quality of perception. In other words: The smaller eye-lens perceives more distinct differences of the lightness than the bigger eye-lens. The size of the eye-lens depends on the size of the eye itself of

course.

to *

It is valid:

$$(1+x)^\alpha = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \binom{\alpha}{n} x^n \quad \alpha \in R \quad |x| < 1$$

with

$$\binom{\alpha}{n} := \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1) \cdot \dots \cdot (\alpha-n+1)}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot \dots \cdot n}$$

This series is called binomial series. With this series it follows because of $\binom{\alpha}{1} = \alpha$
 $(1+x)^\alpha \approx 1 + \alpha x$ for $|x| \ll 1$ $\alpha \in R$

One derivation of the binomial series can be found in Forster [1] "Analysis 1"
§22 at theorem 7 p.182-185.

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 1" 4.Auflage 1984 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001